

GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource:

Guide on choosing an assessment method

Actionable
version

Definition

Guide on choosing an assessment method supports selecting tools, approaches, and infrastructures to evaluate research and researchers in a way that aligns with institutional values and goals.

Relevant SCOPE stages

This guide is most relevant for the SCOPE stages:

- Option for evaluating: Identifying different methods (qualitative, quantitative, narrative, self-assessment, surveys) and data sources.
- Probe deeply: Weighing advantages, limitations, impacts, and unintended consequences of methods before applying them.

When and how to use

- Recruitment & promotion & career assessment: Ensure methods are consistent with institutional values and avoid reliance on journal-based metrics. Base assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation, supported by responsible use of indicators.
- Strategic planning: Use large-scale metrics responsibly for benchmarking and resource allocation at organisational or national level.
- Rewarding & recognition: Consider open science practices, teaching, leadership, societal engagement, and collaboration, not just publications.

Guidance

Start with value

- Define what your organisation values (e.g., openness, interdisciplinarity, quality, societal impact).
- Document values using a Value statement template.

Match method to purpose and level of evaluation

- Individuals: Use qualitative methods (peer review, narrative CV, impact stories). Quantitative indicators should only support expert judgment.
- Groups/organisations: Combine self-assessment, surveys, and carefully chosen metrics
- Large entities (national/disciplinary): Metrics and benchmarking are useful, but should always be contextualised.

Combine methods for balance

- Use more than one method to capture diversity and avoid bias.
- Involve the assessed community in interpreting results.

Use metrics responsibly

- Follow DORA, Leiden Manifesto, Metric Tide and CoARA principles: be clear, transparent, contextual, specific, and fair.
- Avoid journal-based metrics for individual evaluation.
- Always align indicators with assessment objectives.

Choose data infrastructures carefully

- Prefer open, transparent, and interoperable systems (e.g., OpenAIRE, OpenAlex, ORCID).
- Avoid relying only on traditional or commercial databases that limit coverage or reinforce biases.

Further reading

GraspOS SCOPE+i Resources

- Indicators guide1: Responsible use of indicators.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526168>
- Indicators guide 2: Indicators Guide 2: Frameworks and toolboxes for open research <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17181862>
- Open Science Assessment Guide: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525630>
- Assessment Readiness Template: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525577>
- Guide for assembling an assessment team:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525548>
- Value statement template: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15524532>
- Guide on promoting OS contributions in a narrative CV:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525987>
- Guide on principles for responsible research assessment for evaluators and evaluands: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526025>

Other

- European Commission (2019), Indicator frameworks for fostering open knowledge practices in science and scholarship
<https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/445286>
- Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information (2024): <https://barcelona-declaration.org/>
- SCOPE Framework (INORMS, 2023): <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>

